

A thermographical method to assess the power absorption evolution of magnetic nanoparticles through spatio-temporal temperature profiles

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1 Supplementary Experimental

1.1 MNP synthesis and characterization

The morphological characterization of the iron oxide magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) studied was carried out by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The TEM images were obtained using a *Tecnai F20* transmission electron microscope equipped with a Schottky field emission gun, operated at 200 kV accelerating voltage. For these experiments, a drop of the MNP suspension (dispersed in toluene) was deposited on a holey carbon coated micro-grid. TEM images were obtained after the evaporation of the solvent, with a dried grid. One representative image is shown in Fig. S1(a).

The MNPs were assumed spherical and the diameter was obtained through the circular projected area measured in the TEM images. The diameter histogram is shown in Fig. S1(b). This histogram was fitted by a log-normal distribution. The average diameter obtained was 25 nm and the standard deviation, 7 nm.

Fig. S1 (a) Representative TEM image of the sample. (b) Diameter histogram obtained from the measurements of MNP size in TEM images and the corresponding fit of the distribution. The solid line corresponds to the log-normal fit of the distribution and the dashed line to its mean.

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Magnetic measurements were performed using both a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) *Lakeshore* and in a superconducting quantum interference device magnetometer (SQUID) *MPMS-55 Quantum Design*.

Fig. S2 (a) Magnetization as a function of temperature measured through the ZFC-FC protocol and the corresponding blocking temperature distribution obtained from this measurement and the size distribution data. (b) Magnetization loops at room temperature (300 K) and low temperature (5 K).

Magnetization as a function of temperature was measured through the zero-field-cooling (ZFC) and field-cooling (FC) protocols under an applied magnetic field of ~ 1.5 kA/m. Samples were conditioned on a capsule with dispersed MNPs in epoxy resin at a concentration of ~ 0.1 wt%. The results are presented in Fig. S2(a).

The saturation magnetization (M_S) was determined by measuring the magnetization as a function of the applied field at room temperature (300 K) of a powder sample using the aforementioned VSM, obtaining for our sample $M_S = 68$ Am²/kg. The magnetization loop at 5 K was measured in the SQUID on the capsule with MNPs dispersed in epoxy we described before. From this loop it can be seen that the coercivity is $H_C(5\text{ K}) \sim 70$ kA/m. The magnetization loops can be seen in Fig. S2(b).

1.2 MNP glucose coating

Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra of the MNPs used were measured before and after the washing procedure in a *uATR PerkinElmer Spectrum Two* equipment in the range of 450–4000 cm⁻¹, with resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. To perform these measurements, a drop of ferrofluid was placed over the *uATR* crystal and dried with a N₂ flow, resulting in a MNP film covering its entire surface. Interactive baseline corrections and normalisation were performed with the software *Spectrum* from *PerkinElmer*. The obtained spectra are shown in Fig. S3.

Normalization of the spectra was made through the Fe-O peak at 555 cm⁻¹. By comparing both of them, it can be noticed that the ~~O-H stretching modes around 3300 cm⁻¹ are not present in the washed sample and the~~ C-H stretching peaks at 2921 and 2853 cm⁻¹ considerably diminished after washing, which implies that oleic acid coating was removed from the MNPs, leaving them naked and ready for coating.

Fig. S3 FTIR spectra of as prepared MNPs (oleic-acid coated) and the MNPs after a washing procedure with methanol and hot acetone (naked). Characteristic peaks are labelled in the spectra.

1.3 Video processing

As we stated in the main text of this article, the maps obtained from the ordering of the data into a space-time grid present temperature bands for certain time intervals that don't match the general behavior of the temporal evolution during the experiment. These bands are evidenced through steps in the temperature profile plotted as a function of time, such as the ones for the center ($r = 0$) and border ($r = 0.65$ cm) of the PAG (see Fig. S4). These steps are consistent with the temperature sensitivity given by the camera manufacturer (2% of reading or 2 K) and imply that, to generate and process the map, not as many frames are needed as the camera is idle in several of them.

Fig. S4 Temperature increment ΔT as a function of time t for the center ($r = 0$) and border ($r = 0.65$ cm) of a PAG with 0.1 wt% in MNPs. Zones for subsequent curve fitting are numbered from I to IV.

A workaround for this problem is to define a custom time interval between selected frames δt in which the temperature increment variation is greater than the temperature indetermination. Knowing that $\Delta T(t + \delta t) \approx \Delta T(t) + \frac{d(\Delta T)}{dt} \delta t$ and considering temperature sensitivity to be at least 2 K, we get:

$$\delta t \geq 2 \text{ K} \left[\frac{d(\Delta T)}{dt} \right]^{-1}. \quad (\text{S1})$$

According to Eq. S1, the lower threshold value for time interval between frames depends on the temperature increment variation rate, thus it should be different for the heating and cooling periods of the sample. This fact is also evident by looking at the curves in Fig. S4, where the bands are more pronounced at the end of the cooling of the sample.

To define a consistent time interval between frames, the profile for the center of the PAG was divided into 4 zones with distinctive variation rates, as distinguished in Fig. S4. For Zone I, the sample is in thermal equilibrium with its surroundings, thus no temperature increment is displayed and no time-interval adjustment is needed. Zone II represents the power absorption experiment performed in the presence of a non-null magnetic field. Consequently, the sample is heated and the data can be fitted through a curve such as $a - b \exp[-c(t - d)]$, where a , b , c and d are variable fitting parameters that have different values depending on

Fig. S5 Temperature increment ΔT as a function of time t for the center ($r=0$) of a PAG with 0.1 wt% in MNPs, dissected into zones for behavioral fitting. (a) Zone II corresponds to the power absorption experiment and (b-c) zones III and IV to the cooling period of the sample at zero magnetic field.

the zone. Zone III and IV are part of the cooling period of the sample and can be fitted through an exponential decay of the form $b\exp[-c(t-d)]$. The fitting procedure is demonstrated in Fig. S5(a-c).

Once the fitting of the different zones is achieved, the time interval between frames for each of them is calculated using Eq. S1 with $d(\Delta T)/dt$ being the lowest derivative value obtained analytically from the fits. With these intervals determined for each zone, frames are selected conveniently from the original data matrix and then the temperature is interpolated in a regular time grid for all r values. One of the resulting interpolated temperature profiles (the one for $r=0$) is illustrated in Fig. S6.

This procedure to define the time interval between frames for different parts of the experiment can be adapted to other experimental setups by considering the corresponding temperature indetermination instead of “2 K” in Eq. S1.

Fig. S6 Temperature increment ΔT as a function of time t for the center ($r=0$) of a PAG with 0.1 wt% in MNPs before and after the adjustment of time-frame interval and interpolation.